

QUIZ

LAST NAME: ADEKOYA

FIRST NAME: ADEBAYO

PROGRAM CODE: DMCR

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **State the primary purpose of a literature review.**
 - Show a summary of the previous study.
 - Provide key concepts and theories relevant to the topic of study.
 - Review, critique, and synthesize relevant literature to fashion out the new study.¹**
 - Show a broad knowledge of the relevant topic.

2. **Choose from the following analytical methods which, are used for qualitative research.**

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (SAGE, 2008), 46.

- Inductive.**²
- Deductive.
- Post-positivism.
- Statistical analysis.

3. **What is the purpose of writing a research methodology?**

- Process for collecting information.
- Provide for collecting information.
- Show research interest for writing.
- An overview for research design, data proposed sample, plans, methods for data collection and analysis and a rationale for means used.**³

4. **Which among the following is not a qualitative research tradition?**

- Phenomenology.
- Grounded theory.
- Hypothesis.**⁴
- Ethnography.

5. **State among the following, a specific formula for the scope of literature review coverage.**

² Bloomberg and Volpe, 42.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 19.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 39.

- No specific formula to coverage.
- Needs to cover previous research studies.
- Represent the current work-study.
- Concise, relevant information, work that relates to the research problem and logical framework for the study.⁵**

6. **Which among the list below correctly identifies a cited website?**

- Database.
- Access data.
- DOI.⁶**
- URL.

7. **Choose from the list below the reason why the academic writer must report information rightly and correctly.**

- To present new claims only.
- Serve as evidence for all to see.
- Present new claims only.
- Give credit; the accuracy of facts shows tradition that informs the work and so that readers follow or extend the research study.⁷**

8. **Research writer can avoid plagiarism when.**

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* / (University of Chicago Press, 2013), 49.

⁶ Turabian, 88.

⁷Turabian, 86.

- Copied words without citation.
 - The quote in block formation.
 - Writer use quotation mark only.
 - He/she uses relevant source, transcribe words in original and accurately, report the source in reference.⁸**
9. **Choose from the following statement that best describes inductive analysis.**
- Determine study.
 - Data-driven.
 - Data leads to theory⁹**
 - Theory driven.
10. **Among the following statements, choose the one that best describes doctoral candidates.**
- The student in a doctoral program not yet taken a mandated examination.
 - A student is working to take doctoral coursework.
 - A student that works on a research problem for investigation.
 - Students who completed course work passed certification exams involved in some stage of dissertation research.¹⁰**

⁸ Turabian, 208.

⁹ Turabian, 190.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 42.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. California: SAGE Publications, 2008.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.